

Comparison of Three Methods for Quadratic Potential Propagators Part IV

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Mar. 15, 2021

In a series of previous notes (i.e. Parts II and III) we considered three methods for computing the propagator for the problem: $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + k(t)x^2 W + f(t)x (-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}) W$. The first method is based on postulating a form $Q(t) \exp(-i\{ b(t)XX + g(t)YY + g_2(t)XY \})$, inserting into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and equating coefficients of XX etc. The other two methods are based on classical Lagrangians. We argued in Parts II and III that for $f(t)=0$ there is agreement between the methods, but issues arise with the presence of $f(t)x (-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}) W$. In this note, we try to resolve this issue by using $H = p \frac{dx}{dt} - L$ ((1)) where L is the Lagrangian.

In method 2, a Lagrangian with $f(t)x \frac{dx}{dt}$ is considered, but this term is converted to $\frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} x^2 f(t)] - \frac{1}{2} x^2 \frac{df}{dt}$. Thus, the time-dependent oscillator potential is modified and the $\frac{d}{dt} [\dots]$ piece thrown away because it does not affect the classical equations of motion. Method 3 (3) computes the propagator using $Q(t) \exp(i \text{Action})$, so $\frac{d}{dt} [\dots]$ is included and leads to a phase. By using ((1)) we argue that if $f(t)x \frac{dx}{dt}$ exists in the Lagrangian, one must consider a corresponding Hamiltonian of the form: $H = [p + f(t)x][p + f(t)x] / (2m) + k(t)x^2$. This is equivalent to: $p^2/2m + f(t)f(t)x^2 / (2m) + k(t)x^2 + f(t)(1/m)xp - i f(t)/2m$. Thus, we see an extra $f(t)f(t)x^2/2m$ in the Hamiltonian in addition to the $f(t)xp$ type term. This "fixes" the problem of "ff" terms not canceling from the Schrodinger equation in parts II and III. Thus, one must be careful when dealing with velocity dependent potential, but also note that $p = m \frac{dx}{dt} - f(t)x$ now so p as in the electromagnetic case is not simply the momentum of the particle.

Green's Function Approach

In (2), a Lagrangian of the form:

$$L = m/2 \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} + k(t) x^2 + f(t)x \frac{dx}{dt} \quad ((2))$$

is converted into another Lagrangian with $k(t)$ replaced with $k_1(t)$ and the $\frac{dx}{dt}$ potential dropped. To do this, $f(t)x \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} x^2 f(t)] - \frac{1}{2} x^2 \frac{df}{dt}$ is used. The term $\frac{d}{dt} [\dots]$ does not affect the equations of motion and so is eliminated. This appears to be fine classically, but seems to have quantum mechanical implications as a potential in quantum mechanics may still create a phase while not affecting the classical equations of motion as in the Bohm Aharonov situation.

The advantage of "dropping" the $\frac{d}{dt} [\dots]$ term and creating a new Lagrangian is that momentum becomes $m \frac{dx}{dt}$ i.e. the particle momentum. Using the form ((2)) directly yields $p = m \frac{dx}{dt} - f(t)x$ which is no longer simply the particle momentum. Thus, one must be careful when calculating expectation operators of $\frac{d}{dx}$ or $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ as these no longer pertain only to the particle. In addition, there may be an extra field in the problem as in the electromagnetic case where there is a vector potential.

Method (3) of calculating a propagator uses $Q(t)\exp(i \text{ Action})$ and so an additional $d/dt G(t)$ term in L converts immediately into a phase $G(T_f)-G(T_0)$ where $\text{Action} = \int_{t=T_0}^{t=T_f} L dt$. We argue in this note that if one has a Hamiltonian with a term $f(t)x^p$, then one must be careful in choosing an appropriate corresponding Lagrangian. Here, we assume a term $f(t) x dx/dt$ in the Lagrangian and show how the corresponding Hamiltonian is modified.

Hamiltonian for a Potential Containing dx/dt

As in the electromagnetic case where $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot d\mathbf{x}/dt$ appears in the Lagrangian, $f(t)xdx/dt$ may be treated in a similar manner.

$$\text{Thus: } p = dL / d(dx/dt) = m dx/dt - f(t) x \quad ((3))$$

$$H = p dx/dt - L = m/2 dx/dt dx/dt + k(t) xx = 1/2m [p+f(t)x][p+f(t)x] + k(t)xx$$

$$\text{Or } H = pp/2m + f(t)f(t)xx/2m - f(t)x^2/2m \quad ((4))$$

Thus, for a classical problem with an $f(t)xdx/dt$ potential, an extra $f(t)f(t)xx/2m$ term appears in the Hamiltonian ((4)). This extra term is not included in notes Part II and Part III and leads to discrepancies between the Schrodinger equation and Lagrangian approaches which do not exist, as we try to show in this note, if one links the potentials using ((4)).

It may be noted that the momentum ((3)) is now no longer simply that of the particle.

$Q(t) \exp(i \text{ Action})$ Approach To Calculating the Propagator

The approach of (2) of writing a potential $f(t)x dx/dt$ as $d/dt [.5xx f(t)] - .5xx df/dt$ is still useful for calculating the propagator using $Q(t) \exp(i \text{ Action})$ for two reasons. First, an oscillator problem with $k_1(t)xx$ is easily solvable, yielding $b(t) = .5 dA/dt / A$ for the $\exp(-i b(t) XX + \dots)$ portion of the propagator. Secondly, $\int dt d/dt []$ is immediately calculable. One need only keep in mind that the Schrodinger equation ((4)) must be used. We consider here only the form $\exp(-i b(t) XX)$ of the propagator and solve for $b(t)$. Thus, we are not interested in the term $-i f/2m$ (when comparing XX terms in the Schrodinger equation).

First we note that: $Q(t) \exp\{-i [.5dA/dt / A + .5 f]\} ((5))$ is the Lagrangian solution approach from (3).

$$\text{We note (from (3)) that in this approach: } x(t) = XA(T_f-t)/A(T) + Y A(t-T_0)/A(T) \quad ((6))$$

where $A(t)$ is a solution of the classical equations of motion and $A(T_f-T_0)$ is taken to be 0.

Thus: $\int_{t=T_0}^{t=T_f} dt \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2 f(t)]$ (XX piece only) = $-\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2 f(t)$ as $A(T_f - T_0) = 0$. Thus, $-\frac{1}{2}$ is the phase in ((6))

The question is whether ((5)) from the Lagrangian approach satisfies a time dependent Schrodinger equation of the form ((4)). In parts II and III, we considered a Schrodinger equation without the extra $f(t)\dot{x}^2/2m$ and this led to problems. We set $m=1$.

First, note that $A(t)$ is a solution of: $m \frac{dA}{dt} + 2k_1(t)A = 0$ ((7)) where $k_1(t) = k(t) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 f}{dt^2}$ where the second term in $k_1(t)$ follows form $f(t)\dot{x} \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2 f] - \frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2 \frac{df}{dt}$.

In such a case, we know from previous notes that:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{dA}{dt} / A \right) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{df}{dt} = \frac{1}{2m} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{dA}{dt} / A \right) \left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{dA}{dt} / A \right) + k(t) \quad ((8)) \text{ for XX pieces.}$$

$$\text{Thus: } \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = \exp(i \text{ Action}) \left\{ \frac{d}{dt} \left[-\frac{1}{2} \frac{dA}{dt} / A \right] + \frac{1}{2} \frac{df}{dt} \right\} \quad ((9))$$

The term $\frac{1}{2} \frac{df}{dt}$ combines with $k(t)$ on the RHS to form $k_1(t)$.

Thus, we need only consider extra pieces in the Schrodinger equation ((4)) i.e.

$$0 = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2 + f \frac{dA}{dt} / A \left(-\frac{1}{2} \right) \right\} + f^2 \left(-\frac{1}{2} \right) \left\{ \frac{dA}{dt} / A \left(-\frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} f \right\} + \frac{1}{2} f^2 \text{(from ((4)))} \quad ((10))$$

These terms cancel. Thus, the Lagrangian approach $Q(t)\exp(i \text{ Action})$ yields the same propagator as assuming a form $Q(t) \exp\{-i [b(t) \dot{x}^2 + g(t) \dot{x} + g_1(t) x \dot{x}]\}$, inserting into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and equating coefficients of \dot{x}^2 etc.

If there is a potential of the form $f(t)\dot{x} \frac{dx}{dt}$ in the Lagrangian, one must use $H = p \frac{dx}{dt} - L$ to identify corresponding terms in the Hamiltonian. Otherwise problems occur as observed in notes Parts II and III.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if a Lagrangian contains a physical potential of the form $f(t)\dot{x} \frac{dx}{dt}$, then $p = m \frac{dx}{dt} - f(t)\dot{x}$ and is no longer simply the momentum of the particle. This is analogous to the electromagnetic situation. The Hamiltonian is given by $H = p \frac{dx}{dt} - L$ and so contains an extra $\frac{1}{2m} f(t)\dot{x}^2$ term in addition to $f(t) \dot{x} p$. In such a case, using $Q(t)\exp(i \text{ Action})$ to compute the propagator yields the same result as postulating the form $Q(t) \exp(-i [b(t)\dot{x}^2 + g(t)\dot{x} + g_1(t)x\dot{x}])$, inserting into the Schrodinger equation based on $H = p \frac{dx}{dt} - L$ and equating coefficients of \dot{x}^2 etc. It may be noted that the approach of (2) of writing: $f(t) \dot{x} \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2 f] - \frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2 \frac{df}{dt}$ is particularly useful as an oscillator problem with $k_1(t)\dot{x}^2$ is readily solvable and $\int dt \frac{d}{dt} []$ is immediately solvable.

References

1. Cordero-Soto, R. and Lopez, R. and Suazo, E. and Suslov, S. Propagator of a Charged Particle with a Spin in Uniform Magnetic and Perpendicular Electric Fields (2008)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0801.3246.pdf>
2. Keirandish, F. A novel derivation of quantum propagator for time-dependent trapping and control (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1612.07674.pdf>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Path_integral_formulation#Free_particle